

Studies on 2-*N*-Isobutyl/Isopropyl Carboxamidomethyl Thio-3-Aryl-4 (3H) Quinazolinones

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2-*N*-Isobutyl/isopropyl Carboxamidomethyl thio-3-aryl-4 (3H) quinazolinones have been synthesised by the reaction of 2-mercapto-3-aryl-4 (3H) quinazolinones and *N*-isobutyl (or isopropyl)-2-chloroacetamide in ethanol at room temperature.

DURING the last two decades, a number of quinazolinones and their derivatives have been screened for their remarkable biological and pharmacological activities such as antimalarial^{1,2}, antibacterial³, ataractic⁴, diuretic⁵, hypnotic⁶ and anticonvulsant^{7,8}. The anticonvulsant property of 2-methyl-3-*o*-tolyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone⁹ has been reported in mice, rats and dogs. Hypothermic activity in rats and antipyretic activity in rabbits¹⁰ of 2-methyl-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinones have also been reported.

The above observations led Bhargava *et al*^{11,12} to prepare *S*-substituted-2-mercapto-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinones as possible antitubercular¹¹ and antimalarial¹². In the present communication, the syntheses of 2-*N*-isobutyl (or isopropyl)-carboxamidomethylthio-3-aryl-4(3H) quinazolinones from anthranilic acid, aryl isothiocyanates and *N*-isobutyl (or isopropyl)-2-chloroacetamide¹³ have been reported.

Experimental

Melting point of the compounds were recorded on Gallencamp apparatus and are uncorrected. A Varian A60D, a Perkin Elmer 257 and a Coleman analyser were used for NMR, IR and elemental analysis respectively.

2-Mercapto-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinones : These were prepared by the method of Bhargava and Ram¹⁴.

2-(*N*-Isobutylcarboxamidomethylthio)-3-phenyl-4(3H) quinazolinone : 2-Mercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H) quinazolinone (3.2 g) was dissolved in minimum amount of

10% alc. sodium hydroxide. To this was added 1.4 ml of *N*-isobutyl-2-chloroacetamide with constant stirring for an hour at room temp. It was left overnight and a crystalline solid obtained was filtered and washed. Recrystallisation from ethanol afforded white shining crystals, yield 73%, m.p. 150°. TLC: $R_f = 0.32$ (benzene-ether, 3 : 1). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{21}N_3O_2S$: C, 65.39 ; H, 5.72 ; N, 11.44 ; S, 8.71. Found: C, 65.03 ; H, 5.94 ; N, 11.81 ; S, 9.22%. IR, ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3300 (m, N H), 1674(s), 1612(w), 1580(w), 1555(s) cm^{-1} ; NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ : 8.27(1H, m), 6.9-7.8 (9H, m), 3.79(2H, s), 3.07 (2H, dd, $J = 7, 6$ Hz), 1.72(1H, m), 0.84(6H, d, $J = 6$ Hz).

Other *S*-substituted quinazolinones were prepared similarly. Their physical constants are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

2-(*N*-Isopropyl carboxamidomethylthio)-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinones : These were prepared (Table 1) in a similar manner as described above using *N*-isopropyl 2-chloroacetamide. IR and NMR data are recorded in Table 3.

Microbial activity : Some of the compounds of Table 1 (IIb, IIe, IIg and IIh) were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *E. coli* and *A. tumefaciens* ; for antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, *C. neoformans*, *M. canis* and *A. niger* at a maximum tested concentration of 100 $\mu g/ml$ and the compounds IIg and IIh were screened for their antitubercular activity against *M. tuberculosis* H37Ra in Loewenstein-Jensen's medium at a concentration upto 100 $\mu g/ml$. But none of them showed any significant activity.

TABLE I

I, R₁ = C₆H₅ (iso); II, R₁ = C₆H₇¹ (iso)

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF S-SUBSTITUTED-2-MERCAPTO-3-ARYL-4 (3H)-QUINAZOLINONES.

Comp. No.	R ₁	Mol. formula	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)	C%		H%		N%		*R _f values
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
Ia	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	69	145	65.83	66.14	6.52	6.04	11.32	11.02	0.37
Ib	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	92	181	66.43	66.14	6.74	6.04	11.45	11.02	0.37
Ic	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	75	177	66.01	66.14	6.19	6.04	10.85	11.02	0.33
Id	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	82	195	59.21	59.77	5.57	4.98	10.38	10.45	0.36
Ie	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	71	183	63.69	63.47	5.79	5.79	10.48	10.57	0.26
If	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	64	204	64.38	64.23	6.35	6.08	10.46	10.21	0.32
IIa	Phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	65	193	64.82	64.50	5.54	5.38	12.23	11.89	0.36
IIb	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	76	169	64.94	65.38	5.81	5.72	11.74	11.40	0.42
IIc	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	68	210	65.60	65.38	5.99	5.72	11.12	11.40	0.42
IId	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	82	188	65.91	65.38	5.08	5.72	12.00	11.40	0.38
IIe	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	63	216	59.43	58.81	4.87	4.64	10.26	10.83	0.37
IIf	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ S	74	204	62.24	62.64	5.71	5.48	10.82	10.96	0.28
IIg	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	71	221	63.62	63.42	5.20	5.79	10.44	10.58	0.33
IIh	Benzyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	84	211	65.14	65.38	5.68	5.72	11.05	11.40	0.32

*R_f values were measured on developing the TLC plates (adsorbent, silica gel B. D. H.) in Benzene-Ether (3 : 1) mixture.

TABLE 2

NMR* AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF I

Comp. No.	R	δ (ppm)						ν (cm ⁻¹)		
		H-5	Other aromatic protons & -NH-	S-CH ₃	NH-CH ₂ -	-CH-	Me ₂	R	Characteristic IR peaks	
Ia	<i>o</i> -Methyl	8.25 (1H, m)	6.73-7.96 (8H, m)	3.78 (2H, s)	3.09 (2H, dd, <i>J</i> =6,7 Hz)	1.72 (1H, m)	0.81 (6H, d, <i>J</i> =6 Hz)	2.13 (3H, s)	3287 (m), 1658 (s), 1578 (w),	1685 (s), 1615 (w), 1558 (s).
Ib	<i>m</i> -Methyl	8.28 (1H, m)	6.90-7.83 (8H, m)	3.78 (2H, s)	3.08 (2H, dd, <i>J</i> =6,7 Hz)	1.74 (1H, m)	0.83 (6H, d, <i>J</i> =6 Hz)	2.42 (3H, s)	3300 (m), 1648 (s), 1582 (w),	1698 (s), 1616 (w), 1558 (s).
Ic	<i>p</i> -Methyl	8.30 (1H, m)	6.78-7.95 (8H, m)	3.81 (2H, s)	3.10 (2H, dd, <i>J</i> =6,7 Hz)	1.81 (1H, m)	0.83 (6H, d, <i>J</i> =6 Hz)	2.45 (3H, s)	3290 (m), 1662 (s), 1583 (w),	1692 (s), 1618 (w), 1560 (s).
Id	<i>p</i> -Chloro	8.26 (1H, m)	6.85-7.93 (8H, m)	3.80 (2H, s)	3.08 (2H, dd, <i>J</i> =6,7 Hz)	1.78 (1H, m)	0.82 (6H, d, <i>J</i> =6 Hz)	—	3310 (m), 1648 (s), 1578 (w),	1695 (s), 1610 (w), 1550 (s).
Ie	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	8.28 (1H, m)	6.72-7.88 ^a (8H, m)	3.79 (2H, s)	3.09 (2H, dd, <i>J</i> =6,7 Hz)	1.73 (1H, m)	0.83 (6H, d, <i>J</i> =6 Hz)	3.89 (3H, s)	3315 (m), 1650 (s), 1578 (w),	1700 (s), 1620 (w), 1554 (s).
If	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy	8.27 (1H, m)	6.76-7.94 (8H, m)	3.80 (2H, s)	3.10 (2H, dd, <i>J</i> =6,7 Hz)	1.75 (1H, m)	0.84 (6H, d, <i>J</i> =6 Hz)	1.41 (3H, t, <i>J</i> =7 Hz)	3305 (m), 1652 (s), 1580 (w),	1695 (s), 1614 (w), 1548 (s).

4.14
(2H, q,
J=7 Hz)

*NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal standard at 44°. Total number of protons and multiplicity of bands are indicated in parenthesis.

TABLE 3

NMR* AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF II

Comp. No.	R	δ (ppm)					R	ν (cm ⁻¹)		
		H-5	Other aromatic protons & -NH-	S-CH ₂ -	NH-CH-	Me ₂		Characteristic IR peaks		
IIa	H	8.30 (1H, m)	6.78-7.95 (9H, m)	3.73 (2H, s)	4.00 (1H, m)	1.10 (6H, d, J=6 Hz)	—	3300 (m), 1615 (w),	1697 (s), 1582 (w),	1648 (s), 1553 (s).
IIb	<i>o</i> -Methyl	8.29 (1H, m)	6.80-8.02 (8H, m)	3.73 (2H, s)	3.99 (1H, m)	1.08 (6H, d, J=6 Hz)	2.15 (3H, s)	3275 (m), 1615 (w),	1686 (s), 1580 (w),	1650 (s), 1556 (s).
IIc	<i>m</i> -Methyl	8.30 (1H, m)	6.66-7.88 (8H, m)	3.72 (2H, s)	3.99 (1H, m)	1.10 (6H, d, J=6 Hz)	2.40 (3H, s)	3290 (m), 1617 (w),	1698 (s), 1583 (w),	1645 (s), 1556 (s).
II d	<i>p</i> -Methyl	8.28 (1H, m)	6.88-7.74 (8H, m)	3.73 (2H, s)	4.00 (1H, m)	1.10 (6H, d, J=6 Hz)	2.42 (3H, s)	3295 (m), 1615 (w),	1700 (s), 1582 (w),	1643 (s), 1558 (s).
IIe	<i>p</i> -Chloro	8.25 (1H, m)	6.82-7.84 (8H, m)	3.74 (2H, s)	3.94 (1H, m)	1.09 (6H, d, J=6 Hz)	—	3300 (m), 1616 (w),	1700 (s), 1582 (w),	1641 (s), 1558 (s).
II f	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	8.23 (1H, m)	6.79-7.80 (8H, m)	3.71 (2H, s)	3.95 (1H, m)	1.10 (6H, d, J=6 Hz)	3.86 (3H, s)	3320 (m), 1618 (w),	1692 (s), 1583 (w),	1647 (s), 1560 (s).
II g	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy	8.23 (1H, m)	6.85-7.82 (8H, m)	3.71 (2H, s)	3.93 (1H, m)	1.10 (6H, d, J=6 Hz)	1.40 (3H, t, J=7 Hz)	3295 (m), 1617 (w),	1690 (s), 1581 (w),	1662 (s), 1559 (s).
							4.11 (2H, q, J=7 Hz)			

*.NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃, using TMS as internal standard at 44°. Total number of protons and multiplicity of bands are indicated in parenthesis.

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